

Effectiveness of Instructional Learning Strategies as Perceived by BEED Students of Siargao Island Institute of Technology S.Y. 2023-2024

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ABSTRACT-

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of instructional learning strategies as perceived by Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) students at Siargao Island Institute of Technology. A descriptive research design was employed to examine the effectiveness of instructional learning strategies. BEED students from first year to fourth year at Siargao Island Institute of Technology were selected as respondents of the study. A researcher-made questionnaire was utilized as the data collection tool. The data were gathered and analyzed using Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution, Mean and Standard Deviation, Kruskal-Wallis, Shapiro-wilk Test, Spearman Correlation, and Wilcoxon Rank-Sum Test. Findings revealed insights into the demographic profile of the respondents, indicating a majority of female participants within the 20-22 age group, with interpersonal learning styles being the most preferred. Statistical analyses, including non-parametric tests, indicated no significant differences in the effectiveness of instructional learning strategies across demographic factors. However, the Think-Pair-Share strategy emerged as potentially the most effective approach. Recommendations include integrating instructional strategies tailored to interpersonal learning styles, consistent implementation of the Think-Pair-Share method, and ongoing professional development for educators. This research contributes to enhancing teaching quality and student engagement in BEED programs, ultimately improving pre-service teachers' performance in oral communication.

Keywords: instructional learning strategies, BEED students, Siargao Island Institute of Technology, interpersonal learning styles, Think-Pair-Share, professional development, oral communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

Oral communication is a crucial skill that individuals, especially those in the field of education, need to develop. This skill is essential for teachers as it involves interacting with various students from different backgrounds, even with different levels of sensitivity. For teachers, communication skills serve as a tool. Therefore, pre-service teachers need to confidently and effectively deliver lessons. With the guidance of instructors using appropriate instructions suitable for pre-service teachers, it will contribute to the development of oral communication skills for pre-service teachers. Thus, mastering oral communication skills creates an interactive environment that motivates students to engage in the learning process.

In the pursuit of a Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) at Siargao Island Institute of Technology, a significant problem arises. Students face challenges in oral communication, struggling to deliver lessons and express themselves. Teachers find it difficult to expound on topics even when allowed to speak native language. Since teachers are destined to teach, one must master the art of teaching. This situation leads to an investigation of viable solutions. Instructors must cater to the different learning styles of the students, with students demonstrating many preferred learning styles, such as visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. It is essential to identify and incorporate these preferences into instructional approaches for better learning to happen.

In a recent study, teachers were found to benefit from understanding how learners learn, influencing teachers teaching practices (Evans & Waring, 2006). This idea emphasizes the significant role teachers play in shaping students behavior in the classroom. By tailoring instruction to suit students preferred learning styles, teachers can effectively address areas where students may struggle.

The absence of effective instructional learning strategies at SIIT can have a negative impact on the performance of BEED students. The researchers initiated this study to identify the most effective instructional learning strategies as perceived by BEED students at SIIT. The study also aimed to propose potential enhancements and refinements to these recognized instructional learning strategies. By identifying the most effective instructional learning strategies perceived by BEED students, the study can inform educators and administrators about methods that resonate best with learners, thus enhancing teaching quality and student engagement, contributing to the improvement of pre-service teachers' performance, specifically in oral communication.

1.1 Literature Review

Instructional learning strategies are fundamental in fostering students' oral communication abilities. Moposita (2021) highlights the VARK (Visual, Auditory, Reading/Writing, and Kinesthetic) technique as an effective method to enhance vocal skills in English learning, improving engagement and aligning with individual student objectives. Similarly, Antonello et al. (2018) emphasize the importance of understanding how students learn, which enables educators to design strategies tailored to diverse learning needs and enhance educational outcomes.

Jamulia (2018) stresses the significance of recognizing individual traits during the learning process, linking diverse learning styles with student success. Siddiqui et al. (2019) add that understanding cognitive preferences increases motivation and fosters better learning outcomes. Squadron (2023) underscores that incorporating instructional learning styles addresses barriers, such as challenges in oral communication, and improves overall performance.

Strategies for Enhanced Engagement

Man Rama (2019) and Moposita (2021) argue that instructional strategies like the Learning Style-Based Instructional Program improve oral expression achievements. Collaborative learning, a method highlighted by Agustina (2022), fosters teamwork, reduces classroom stress, and aligns with individual learning styles, leading to better understanding and confidence in communication.

Differentiated Instruction, as studied by Arianto et al. (2023), employs diverse methods such as presentations and games, which significantly enhance students' spoken English abilities and boost their confidence. Loreto (2022) advocates for integrating innovative methods like vlogging to improve self-awareness, creativity, and oral communication.

The Role of Teachers and Technology

Teachers are pivotal in developing students' communication skills. Rao (2019) suggests using collaborative activities and game-based learning to motivate students, while Samifannia and Faramarz (2020) emphasize learner-centered approaches that focus on authentic tasks and interactive teaching. Fedorenko (2023) notes the role of interactive technologies in creating collaborative and engaging learning environments, which support both student and teacher growth.

1.2 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework of the Study

This study was supported by the Multiple Intelligences theory presented by Dr. Serhat Kurt (2020) and the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) as outlined by Matthew E. Poehner (as cited in The Modern Language Journal, 96(4), 610-622, 2012).

The Multiple Intelligences Theory, as presented by Dr. Serhat Kurt with its introduction by Howard Gardner, posits that intelligence is not a singular entity but comprises various distinct forms. Dr. Serhat Kurt emphasizes that identifying a student's intellect benefits both students and instructors. This identification enables the instructor to select relevant activities that are suited to the student's skills, thereby guiding their learning journey more effectively (Kurt, 2020).

The Zone of Proximal Development is the space between what a learner can do on their own and what they can do with adult instruction or in partnership with more capable classmates. In keeping with the notion of ZPD, It is argued that as learners go from a cooperative to an autonomous style of self-assessment, it is stated that their efforts to self-assess must be properly managed so that it will help learners enhance their metacognitive abilities, contributing to a more effective learning experience (Matthew E. Poehner, The Modern Language Journal 96 (4), 610-622, 2012).

This study examined the dependent variable, which is oral communication skills, and the independent variables, including traditional learning approaches, think-pair-share, role-playing and Socratic method used by teachers as perceived by BEED students at SIIT. The traditional approaches remain prevalent in classrooms, but the effectiveness of this approach depends on the teacher's ability to implement them appropriately. Teachers uses the Think-pair-share method, which aligns with the zone of proximal development. However, difficulties develop when some pupils rely excessively on their more knowledgeable peers. Role-playing is commonly used, providing students with an active role in the learning process. While the socratic method is widely used, a common issue arises when questions are posed without considering students readiness.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of instructional learning strategies as perceived by the Bachelor of Elementary Education students at Siargao Island Institute of Technology, Dapa, Surigao del Norte. Specifically, it sought to answer to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondent in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Year level
 - 1.4 Civil Status
 - 1.5 Preferred Learning Style
2. At what level do students perceive the effectiveness of instructional learning strategies like:
 - 2.1 Traditional Learning styles Approach
 - 2.2 Think – pair – share
 - 2.3 Role Playing
 - 2.4 Socratic Method
3. Is there a significant difference between the effectiveness of instructional learning strategies when grouped according to the profiled variables?
4. Which among the instructional learning strategies perceived by the students is the most effective?
5. Based on the result of the study, what recommendation can be proposed?

II. METHOD

This study employed a quantitative research approach using a descriptive survey design to gather data on the opinions, perceptions, and attitudes of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) students at Siargao Island Institute of Technology (SIIT). The respondents, who ranged from first-year to fourth-year students with the total of 158, were selected using a randomized roll paper method, ensuring equal

selection opportunities. The study was conducted within the SIIT campus, strategically scheduled during students' vacant hours to minimize disruptions. A researcher-made questionnaire, which was validated by experts, was used to collect data, focusing on respondents' profiles, the effectiveness of instructional strategies, and proposed recommendations.

Data were analyzed using various statistical tools, such as frequency counts, Kruskal-Wallis tests, and Spearman correlation, to evaluate the demographic profile and the effectiveness of instructional strategies while identifying trends and relationships. Ethical considerations, including informed consent and confidentiality, were strictly observed. The study adhered to rigorous research standards based on Lincoln and Guba's framework, ensuring the validity, reliability, credibility, and dependability of its findings. This comprehensive methodology supported the study's goal of understanding the instructional strategies perceived as effective by BEED students at SIIT.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1. *Profile of the respondents*

Profile		F	%
Age	17-19	51	32.28
	20-22	90	56.96
	23 years old and above	17	10.76
Sex	Female	137	86.71
	Male	21	13.29
Civil Status	Married	4	2.53
	Single	154	97.47
Year Level	1 st year	40	25.32
	2 nd year	41	25.95
	3 rd year	38	24.05
	4 th year	39	24.68

The respondents were predominantly female (86.71%) and single (97.47%), with most aged 20-22 years (56.96%), followed by those aged 17-19 years (32.28%) and a smaller portion aged 23 and above (10.76%). The majority of participants were students, evenly distributed across year levels: 1st year (25.32%), 2nd year (25.95%) and 3rd year (24.05%), 4th year (24.68%).

Table 2. Descriptive analysis on the factors when grouped according to age

Variable	Age	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Traditional Learning Styles	17-19years old	3.2	3.28	0.444	0.062
Traditional Learning Styles	20-22 years old	3.4	3.33	0.459	0.048
Traditional Learning Styles	Above 23 years old	3.4	3.38	0.393	0.095
Think-Pair-Share	20-22years old	3.6	3.5	0.432	0.045
Think-Pair-Share	Above 23 years old	3.6	3.54	0.352	0.085
Role Play	17-19 years old	3.4	3.45	0.464	0.065
Role Play	20-22 years old	3.4	3.40	0.467	0.049
Role Play	Above 23 years old	3.4	3.38	0.307	0.075
Socratic Method	17-19years old	3.4	3.43	0.451	0.063
Socratic Method	20-22 years old	3.6	3.50	0.443	0.047
Socratic Method	Above 23 years old	3.2	3.36	0.46	0.111

The table above (Table 2) shows the descriptive analysis on the factors when grouped according to their age. Two of the measures of central tendency such as median and mean provides an exact representation of the entire collected data which can be seen on the said table. Furthermore, the standard deviation (SD) with the standard error (SE) shows how dispersed is the data and again showcased in Table 6. Lastly, with negligible difference, the response of students ages 20-22 years to role play is the most dispersed, while students ages 23 years and above perceive think-pair-share as having the most significant impact on student behavior based on the mean.

Table 3. Analysis on significant differences on each factors grouped according to age.

Variable	Statistical Test	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Traditional	Kruskal-Wallis	0.745>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Think-Pair-Share	Kruskal-Wallis	0.693>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Role Play	Kruskal-Wallis	0.709>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Socratic Method	Kruskal-Wallis	0.462>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant

Table 3 shows that, using the Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test, there are no significant differences among all the variables (Traditional Learning Styles, Think-Pair-Share, Role Play, and Socratic Method) as the p-values (0.745, 0.693, 0.709, 0.462) are greater than the level of significance (α) of 0.05.

Table 4. Descriptive analysis on the factors when grouped according to sex.

Variables	Sex	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Traditional Learning Styles	Male	3.2	3.27	0.421	0.092
Traditional Learning Styles	Female	3.4	3.33	0.45	0.038
Think-Pair-Share	Male	3.6	3.52	0.44	0.092
Think-Pair-Share	Female	3.6	3.47	0.445	0.038
Role Play	Female	3.6	3.42	0.452	0.039
Socratic Method	Male	3.6	3.61	0.427	0.093

Socratic Method	Female	3.4	3.44	0.447	0.088
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Table 4 shows the descriptive analysis on the factors when grouped according to their Sex. Two of the measures of central tendency such as median and mean provides an exact representation of the entire collected data which can be seen on the said table. Furthermore, the standard deviation with the standard error shows how dispersed the data. Lastly, with negligible difference, the response of the female students on the role play is the most dispersed and according to male students, Socratic method has most significant based on the mean.

Table 5. Analysis on significant differences on each factors grouped according to sex.

Variables	Statistical Test	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Traditional	Kruskal-Wallis	0.552>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Think-Pair-Share	Kruskal-Wallis	0.552>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Role Play	Kruskal-Wallis	0.366>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Socratic Method	Kruskal-Wallis	0.0682>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant

Table 5 shows that, using the Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test, there are no significant differences among all the variables (Traditional Learning Styles, Think-Pair-Share, Role Play, and Socratic Method) as the p-values (0.552, 0.552, 0.336, 0.0682) are greater than the level of significance (α) of 0.05.

Table 6. Analysis on significant differences on each factors grouped according to year level.

Variables	Statistical Test	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Traditional	Wilcoxon Rank	0.405>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Think-Pair-Share	Wilcoxon Rank	0.259>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Role Play	Wilcoxon Rank	0.664>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Socratic Method	Wilcoxon Rank	0.829>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant

Table 6 shows that, using the Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test, there are no significant differences among all the variables (Traditional Learning Styles, Think-Pair-Share, Role Play, and Socratic Method) as the p-values (0.405, 0.259, 0.664, 0.829) are greater than the level of significance (α) of 0.05.

Table 7. Analysis on significant differences on each factors grouped according to Civil Status.

Variables	Statistical Test	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Traditional	Kruskal-Wallis	0.146>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Think-Pair-Share	Kruskal-Wallis	0.00906<0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant
Role Play	Kruskal-Wallis	0.111>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Socratic Method	Kruskal-Wallis	0.0343>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant

Table 7 shows that, using the Kruskal-Wallis test, there are no significant differences among the variables (Traditional Learning Style, Role Play, and Socratic Method) as the p-values (0.146, 0.111, 0.0343) are greater than the level of significance (α) of 0.05. However, for the Think-Pair-Share method, there is a significant difference as the p-value (0.00906) is less than the level of significance (α) 0.05.

Table 8. *Analysis on significant differences on each factors grouped according to Preferred Learning Style.*

Variables	Statistical Test	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Traditional	Wilcoxon Rank	0.195>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Think-Pair-Share	Wilcoxon Rank	0.256>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Role Play	Wilcoxon Rank	0.954>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Socratic Method	Wilcoxon Rank	0.856>0.05	Fail to reject H ₀	Not Significant

Table 8 shows that, using the Kruskal-Wallis test, there are no significant differences among all the variables (Traditional Learning Style, Role Play, and Socratic Method) as the p-values (0.195, 0.256, 0.954, 0.856) are greater than the level of significance (α) of 0.05.

Table 9. *Descriptive analysis on the factors when grouped according to year level.*

Variables	Year Level	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Tradional Learning Styles	1 st year	3.4	3.32	0.47	0.074
Tradional Learning Styles	2 nd year	3.2	3.29	0.427	0.067
Tradional Learning Styles	3 rd year	3.2	3.26	0.467	0.076
Tradional Learning Styles	4 th year	3.4	3.41	0.42	0.067
Think-Pair-Share	1 st year	3.4	3.35	0.524	0.083
Think-Pair-Share	2 nd year	3.6	3.55	0.41	0.064
Think-Pair-Share	3 rd year	3.7	3.56	0.377	0.061
Role Play	1 st year	3.4	3.43	0.483	0.076
Role Play	2 nd Year	3.4	3.40	0.43	0.063
Role Play	3 rd Year	3.5	3.49	0.359	0.058
Role Play	4 th year	3.4	3.33	0.516	0.8
Socratic Method	1st year	3.6	3.42	0.493	0.078
Socratic Method	2 nd year	3.4	3.48	0.395	0.062
Socratic Method	3 rd year	3.4	3.44	0.419	0.068
Socratic Method	4 th year	3.6	3.50	0.485	0.078

Table 9 shows descriptive analysis of the instructional learning strategies across different year levels. The measures of central tendency, such as the median and mean, offer an accurate representation of the collected data, as illustrated in the table. Moreover, the standard deviation (SD) and standard error (SE) indicate the dispersion of the data, which is also detailed in Table 13. Lastly with negligence difference, the response of 1st-year students to the think-pair-share method is the most dispersed, while

3rd-year students perceive the think-pair-share method to have the most significant impact on student behavior based on the mean

Table 10. *Descriptive analysis on the factors when grouped according to Civil Status.*

Variables	Civil Status	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Traditional Learning Styles	Single	3.4	3.33	0.45	0.038
Traditional Learning Styles	Married	3.2	3.27	0.421	0.092
Think-Pair-Share	Single	3.6	3.47	0.445	0.44
Think-Pair-Share	Married	3.6	3.52	0.44	0.096
Role Play	Single	3.4	3.42	0.462	0.039
Role Play	Married	3.4	3.35	0.374	0.082
Socratic Method	Single	3.4	3.44	0.447	0.038
Socratic Method	Married	3.6	3.61	0.427	0.093

Table 10 shows the descriptive analysis on the factors when grouped according to their Civil Status. Two of the measures of central tendency such as median and mean provides an exact representation of the entire collected data which can be seen on the said table. Furthermore, the standard deviation with the standard error shows how dispersed is the data and again showcased in Table 14. Lastly, with negligible difference, the response of single respondents for role play is the most dispersed, and according to married respondents, the socratic method has the most significance based on the mean.

Table 11. *Descriptive analysis on the factors when grouped according to preferred*

Variables	Preferred Learning Style	Median	Mean	SD
Traditional Learning Styles	Bodily-Kinesthetic	3	3.18	0.388
Traditional Learning Styles	Interpersonal	3.4	3.34	0.459
Traditional Learning Styles	Logical-Mathematical	3	3	0.3
Traditional Learning Styles	Spatial	3.2	3.28	0.46
Traditional Learning Styles	Verbal Linguistic	3.4	3.40	0.443
Think-Pair-Share	Bodily-Kinesthetic	3.4	3.47	0.348
Think-Pair-Share	Interpersonal	3.6	3.47	3.413
Think-Pair-Share	Logical-Mathematical	2.8	3.13	0.757
Think-Pair-Share	Spatial	3.3	3.39	0.435
Think-Pair-Share	Verbal Linguistic	3.8	3.56	0.5
Role Play	Bodily-Kinesthetic	3.2	3.38	0.41
Role Play	Interpersonal	3.4	3.43	0.437
Role Play	Logical-Mathematical	3.4	3.33	0.503
Role Play	Spatial	3.4	3.41	0.411
Role Play	Verbal Linguistic	3.5	3.41	0.516
Socratic Method	Bodily-Kinesthetic	3.4	3.46	0.411
Socratic Method	Interpersonal	3.6	3.49	0.44
Socratic Method	Logical-Mathematical	3	3.27	0.462
Socratic Method	Spatial	3.4	3.43	0.44
Socratic Method	Verbal Linguistic	3.5	3.44	0.484

Table 11 shows the descriptive analysis on the factors when grouped according to their Preferred Style. Two of the measures of central tendency such as median and mean provides an exact representation of the entire collected data which can be seen on the said table. Furthermore, the standard deviation with the standard error shows how dispersed is the data and again showcased in Table 11. Lastly, with negligible difference, the response of the preferred learning styles students on the effectiveness of logical mathematical is the most dispersed and according to think-pair-share, interpersonal has most significant based on the mean.

Significant difference between the variables traditional, think-pair-share, role play, and Socratic method

Table 12. Descriptive analysis on the factors (or variables)

Variables	Min	Max	Median	Mean	SD	SE
Traditional Learning	2.2	4	3.4	3.32	0.446	0.035
Think-Pair-Share	2	4	3.6	3.48	0.443	0.035
Role play	2	4	3.4	3.41	0.45	0.036
Socratic Method	2.4	4	3.4	3.46	0.447	0.036

Table 12 shows the descriptive analysis on the factors when grouped according to their age. Two of the measures of central tendency such as median and mean provides an exact representation of the entire collected data which can be seen on the said table. Furthermore, the standard deviation (SD) with the standard error (SE) shows how dispersed is the data and again showcased in Table 11. Lastly, with negligible difference, the socratic method is the most dispersed, while think-pair-share has the most significance based on the mean.

Table 13. Analysis on significant differences between the variables or factors

Variables	Statistical Test	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Variables	Kruskal-Wallis	0.00628 < 0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 13 shows that using Kruskal-Wallis test for normality, the p-value of 0.00628 is obviously less than the level of significance (α) which is 0.05, indicating that there is significant difference between the factors or variables.

Table 14. Post-hoc test for the different variables in terms of the perceived effectiveness of instructional learning strategies .

Variables	Group1	Group2	P-value	Interpretation
Score	Traditional Learning Styles	Think-Pair-Share	0.00135 < 0.05	Significant
Score	Traditional Learning Styles	Role Play	0.0579 > 0.05	Not
Score	Traditional Learning Styles	Socratic Method	0.00446 < 0.05	Significant
Score	Think-Pair-Share	Role Play	0.191 > 0.05	Not
Score	Think-Pair-Share	Socratic Method	0.716 > 0.05	Not
Score	Role Play	Socratic Method	0.344 > 0.05.	Not

Table 14 shows that there are significant differences in scores between Traditional Learning Styles and both Think-Pair-Share (p-value = 0.00135) and the Socratic Method (p-value = 0.00446). However, there are no significant differences between Traditional Learning Styles and Role Play (p-value = 0.0579), Think-Pair-Share and Role Play (p-value = 0.191), Think-Pair-Share and the Socratic Method (p-value = 0.716), or Role Play and the Socratic Method (p-value = 0.344).

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concluded that the interpersonal learning style was the most preferred among BEED students, highlighting the need for tailored instructional approaches to meet this preference. The Think-Pair-Share strategy emerged as a highly effective method, with a notable mean score, underscoring its potential for broader application across the BEED curriculum. Furthermore, the analysis revealed low to moderate correlations among different instructional strategies, suggesting opportunities for combining these methods to improve learning outcomes. These findings emphasize the importance of aligning instructional strategies with students' preferences and diversifying approaches to cater to varied learning styles and demographic factors.

Based on these conclusions, it is recommended to implement instructional strategies that align with the interpersonal learning style and integrate the Think-Pair-Share strategy consistently into BEED curricula. Faculty should be provided with training and resources to enhance the effective application of this method. Further research is encouraged to explore the combination of correlated instructional strategies for improved outcomes. Educational institutions should prioritize diversity and inclusion in selecting instructional methods, ensuring they accommodate demographic variations. Regular evaluation mechanisms should be established to assess the effectiveness of these strategies, while professional development workshops should prepare educators to adapt their teaching methods. Lastly, fostering collaborative learning opportunities is essential for enriching peer interaction and overall learning experiences.

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